

Determination of antiepileptics in whole blood by LC-MS/MS

Detected substances:

Carbamazepine (CBZ), Carbamazepine-10,11-epoxide (CBZE), Lacosamide (LA), Lamotrigine (LMT), Levetiracetam (LEV), Oxcarbazepine (OX), Phenobarbital (PB), Phenytoin (PNT), Valproic acid (VPA), 10,11-Dihydro-10-hydroxycarbamazepine (DHCB)

Biological sample:

50 µL of venous blood

Reagent preparation:

- **Mobile phase A:** Ammonium acetate 5 mM in water (pH 4.5) = 2.5 mL of 1M acetic acid, diluted to 500 mL with MilliQ water. Adjust pH with pure acetic acid.

- **Mobile phase B:** Ammonium acetate 5 mM in ACN:Water (pH 4.5) = 2.5 mL 1M acetic acid + 25 mL water, make up to 500 mL ACN. Adjust pH with pure acetic acid.

- Acetic acid 1M = 3.854 g solid acetate in 50 mL MilliQ water. Store in the refrigerator.

- **Mobile phase for reconstitution:** A:B 60:40 = 3 mL A + 2 mL B

Calibration curve concentrations (µg/mL) and QCs:

Group	Cal 1	Cal 2	Cal 3	Cal 4	Cal 5	Cal 6	Cal 7
A	10	20	30	45	67,5	101,25	202,5
B	2,5	5	7,5	11,25	16,875	25,3125	50,625
C	1	2	3	4,5	6,75	10,125	20,25
D	0,5	1	1,5	2,25	3,375	5,0625	10,125
	LOQ	QC _{low}		QC _{medium}		QC _{high}	
A: VPA B: DHCB, LEV, PNT C: LA, LMT, CBZ, PB D: OX, CBZE							

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Standard stock solutions:

- **A:** VPA at 20,25 mg/mL
- **B:** DHCB, LEV, PNT at 20,25 mg/mL
- **C:** LA, LMT, CBZ, PB at 8,1 mg/mL
- **D:** CBZE, OX at 4,045 mg/mL

Calibrator solutions:

- **Calibrator 7:**
 - For VPA (Cal A)= 400 μ L at 20,25 mg/mL + 600 μ L MeOH \rightarrow 1000 μ L
 - For the rest (Cal BCD)= 100 μ L standards (x9) + 100 μ L MeOH \rightarrow 1000 μ L
- **Calibrator 6:**
 - 450 μ L cal 7 + 450 μ L MeOH \rightarrow 900 μ L
- **Calibrator 5:**
 - 600 μ L cal 6 + 300 μ L MeOH \rightarrow 900 μ L
- **Calibrator 4:**
 - 600 μ L cal 5 + 300 μ L MeOH \rightarrow 900 μ L
- **Calibrator 3:**
 - 600 μ L cal 4 + 300 μ L MeOH \rightarrow 900 μ L
- **Calibrator 2:**
 - 600 μ L cal 3 + 300 μ L MeOH \rightarrow 900 μ L
- **Calibrator 1:**
 - 450 μ L cal 2 + 450 μ L MeOH \rightarrow 900 μ L

Internal standard solutions:

- **Group A:** VPA, DHCB, LEV, PNT
 - 320 μ L (x4) at 100 μ g/mL \rightarrow 1280 μ L
- **Group B:** LA, LMT, CBZ, PB
 - 128 μ L (x4) at 100 μ g/mL \rightarrow 512 μ L
- **Group C:** CBZE, OX
 - 64 μ L (x2) at 100 μ g/mL \rightarrow 128 μ L

Total 1920 μ L + 80 μ L MeOH \rightarrow 2 mL IS solution

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Preparation of blood for the calibration curve and QCs:

- Prepare 1 mL of blood at room temperature for each concentration: 25 µL Cal A + 25 µL Cal BCD + 950 µL blank blood → 1 mL
- Shake for 30 minutes.

Extraction:

- Pipet 50 µL of blood into a 2 mL Eppendorf tube.
- Add 100 µL MilliQ water, vortex, add 20 µL IS (for blanks: 20 µL MeOH), vortex, add 800 µL cold ACN.
- Manually turn the tubes over 3 times and then vortex.
- Let them rest 10 minutes at room temperature.
- Centrifuge for 10 minutes at 14,500 rpm.
- Evaporate the supernatant.
- Reconstitute in 50 µL mobile phase.
- Transfer to inserts and centrifuge. Inject 2 µL into ESI+ and 5 µL into ESI-

LC-MS/MS conditions:

- Liquid chromatography:

ACQUITY UPLC CORTECS T3 column (2.1 x 100mm, 1.6 µm) + VanGuard 3/Pk precolumn (2.1 x 5mm, 1.6). T = 45°C. Purge liquid: Water:ACN 90:10

Method I: Negative ionization						
Gradient	Time (min)					
% MP	0	1	1.5	2.5	2.6	4
A	80	40	2	2	80	80
B	20	60	98	98	20	20

Flow: 0.5 mL/min

Method II: Positive ionization								
Gradient	Time (min)							
% MP	0	0.22	0.5	2.22	3	3.8	3.9	6
A	90	73	73	69	2	2	90	90
B	10	27	27	31	98	98	10	10

Flow: 0.5 mL/min

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- Mass spectrometry:

Method I transitions (ESI-)					
Compound	Parent (m/z)	Fragment (m/z)	Dwell (s)	Cone (V)	Colision (eV)
PNT	251.05	101.96	0.015	6	20
	251.05	77	0.015	6	26
PNT-d10	261.08	105.99	0.015	32	22
PB	231.1	42	0.015	30	15
	231.1	188.1	0.015	30	10
PB-d5	236.15	193.5	0.015	30	10
VPA	143.1	143.101	0.015	5	6
	143.14	143.13	0.015	35	6
VPA-d4	147.01	147.01	0.015	25	5

Method II transitions (ESI+)					
Compound	Parent (m/z)	Fragment (m/z)	Dwell (s)	Cone (V)	Colision (eV)
CBZ	237.16	178.97	0.063	40	32
	237.16	165.13	0.063	40	36
CBZ-d10	247	204.1	0.063	2	31
LMT	256.05	144.92	0.022	2	32
	256.05	158.96	0.022	2	26
LMT-d3	261.09	191.26	0.022	2	20
LA	251.05	91.12	0.022	20	28
	251.05	91.12	0.022	20	28
LA-13Cd6	255.1	120.1	0.022	40	30
LEV	171.2	126.1	0.038	15	13
	171.2	98.15	0.038	15	22
LEV-d6	177.25	132.2	0.038	15	13
OX	253.2	208	0.052	50	27
	253.2	180.02	0.052	50	28
OX-13C6	259.19	171.23	0.052	30	20
CBZE	253.17	180.08	0.052	16	22
	253.17	167.08	0.052	16	32
CBZE-13C6	259.18	186.07	0.052	2	30
DHCB	255.2	237.2	0.022	18	8
	255.2	194.2	0.022	18	20
DHCB-13C6	261.15	243.25	0.022	18	8